

Synthesis and Characterizations of Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles Antimalarial (Arthemeter) Drug Delivery System

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Abstract:- Malaria is endemic and a life-threatening disease been caused by the bite of a female anopheles mosquito which destroys the red blood cells. Nano carrier drug delivery system is of great interest in malaria research for improving the quality of health care delivery. This research work focused on development of inorganic silica nanoparticles as efficient delivery system for antimalarial drug of Artemeter (ATM). The mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNPs) both amino modified mobile crystalline matter (aMCM-41) and mobile crystalline matter (MCM-41) were synthesized by co-condensation and sol-gel methods respectively. ATM antimalarial drugs were loaded in both MCM-41 and aMCM-41 with chloroform as the solvent under varying effects of time (1hr, 3hrs and 6hrs), pH (Neutral and Acidic) and temperature (25°C and 40°C) respectively. The synthesized nano carrier (MCM-41 and aMCM-41) and nanodrugs fit well for their expected properties as depicted from Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm, UV-Visible Spectroscopy, *in vitro* kinetic study and *in vivo* measurement using *P. berghei* NK65. The drug loading capacities (DLC) and Entrapment Efficiency (EE) of the nano carriers were determined using UV-Visible spectrophotometry. The FT-IR depicts major functional groups of the silanol group (Si-OH) and siloxane (Si-O) which absorbed at 3450 cm⁻¹ and 964 cm⁻¹ respectively for MCM-41, while after amino functionalization the silanol group was obstructed. The nanodrugs show only the functional groups of MSNPs due to the drugs encapsulation. The synthesized MSNPs (MCM-41 and aMCM-41) have average pore diameter of 5.1617 nm and 2.9778 nm respectively as expected for the mesoporous materials which decreases due to adsorption of ATM encapsulated in MCM-41 and ATM encapsulated in aMCM-41 to 4.395 nm and 2.5551 nm accordingly. ATM encapsulates in MCM-41 and aMCM-41: MCM-41 ⊃ ATM and aMCM-41 ⊃ ATM have the highest DLC of 79% and 81% and EE of 65% and 67% respectively which shows the size effects of MCM-41 compared to aMCM-41. The *in-vitro* kinetic studies of the drugs and their nanodrugs showed that aMCM-41 loaded ATM has the highest percentage of drugs released compared with MCM-41. The *in-vivo* measurement of the combination of ATM loaded MCM-41 and aMCM-41 shows better bio performance for plasmodia clearance in infected mice on

the third day compared to the parent drugs. Therefore; this shows the satisfactory of the synthesized nano carrier for the delivery of the antimalarial drugs.

Keywords:- Antimalarial Drugs (Arthemeter), Delivery System, Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles (MSNPs), Co-condensation and Sol-gel, Encapsulate.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malaria is endemic and a life-threatening disease been caused by the bite of a female anopheles mosquito which destroys the red blood cells. Many phases has been on ground to fight the problem of resistant to antimalarial drugs but the idea of nano medicine is gaining attention due to its very high impact because the size of drugs can be reduced for better improvement. Also, due to the problem of insolubility, toxicity and instability we need to use nano medicine. Drug delivery systems like Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNPs) control the rate at which a drug is released and the location in the body where it is released. It can be described as a formulation that controls the rate and period of drug delivery (i.e. time-release dosage) and targets specific areas of the body which also helps to overcome the problem of drug insolubility, toxicity and instability. The MSNPs are introduced as chemically and thermally stable nanomaterials with well-defined and controllable morphology and porosity. These particles possess external and internal surfaces that can be selectively functionalized with multiple organic and inorganic groups. Therefore, Mesoporous silica nanoparticles with different surface chemistry were used as drugs (Artemether and Lumefantrine) delivery system to study its influence on drug delivery and antimalarial activity of arthemeter and lumefantrine.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials Used

Artemether active agent, Chloroform, Distilled water, Hydrochloric acid, SLS (Sodium lauryl sulphate), Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, Sodium hydroxide, 3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane (APTES), Methanol.

B. Methods

Fig. 1: Basic Reaction Scheme for the Synthesis of Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles (Beck et al (1992), JACS)

➤ Synthesis of MCM-41 with Variation in the Ratio of CTAB

480 g of distilled water was accurately measured into a round bottom flask, then 1 or 1.355 or 1.642g of CTAB was weighed and added to the 480g of distilled water as the case may be, 7ml of 2M NaOH was added under stirring for the system to be in alkaline medium. The temperature was set to 80°C, a clear solution was observed at 50°C, at this temperature 6.7ml Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) was added to the solution in drop using a pipette. Once the temperature reached 80°C the mixture was stirred for 2 hours, at this point a milky solution was observed. It was centrifuge and filtered, the residue was washed to neutralize the pH. The washed residue was left to dry over night and placed in a crucible for calcinations, that is, it was heated at high temperature of 550°C for 5 hours. Note that ratio of CTAB was varied to vary the pore size, pore volume and the size of synthesized mesoporous silica nanoparticles.

➤ Synthesis of Amino Modified MCM-41 with Varied Amount of CTAB

480g of distilled water was accurately measured into a round bottom flask, then 1 or 1.355 or 1.642g of CTAB was weighed and added to the 480g of distilled water as the case may be, 7ml of 2M NaOH was added under stirring for the system to be in alkaline medium. The temperature was set to 80°C, a clear solution was observed at 50°C, at this temperature 6.7ml Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) was added to the solution in drop using a pipette followed by the addition of 0.54ml, 3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane (APTES). Once the temperature reached 80°C the mixture was stirred for 2 hours, at this point a milky solution was observed. It was centrifuge and filtered, the residue was washed to neutralize the pH. The washed residue was left to dry over night. Note that ratio of CTAB was varied to vary the pore size, pore volume and the size of synthesized mesoporous silica nanoparticles. Also, Note: it was not calcined because APTES cannot withstand the temperature of 550°C. Solvent extraction process was used.

➤ Encapsulation of Antimalaria Drugs (Artemether) into MCM-41 and Amino Modified MCM-41

40 mg of artemether was weighed and dissolved in 10 mL chloroform; the solution was added to a 10mg of the carrier (MCM-41 or Amino Modified MCM-41), the system was covered with cotton wool then shake under different conditions of time (1hr, 3hrs and 6hrs), pH (Basic and Acidic Medium) and temperature (25°C and 40°C), this was done to determine the best loading condition for the drug. After shaking, the solution was filtered and the residue was slightly washed. The filtrate is called the supernatant while the residue is called the composite; the absorbance of the supernatant was checked on the uv-spectrophotometer to determine the concentration of unloaded and loaded drugs in MCM-41 and Amino Modified MCM-41.

➤ In-vitro Kinetic Release Study

Antimalarial loaded silica (composite) equivalent of 2 mg of the antimalarial drug were singly weighed and suspended in 5mL of 0.5% Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) Buffer. This suspension was then place in dialysis bag with 10KDa molecular weight cut-off and was immersed into 50mL of 0.5% SLS at 37 °C with continuous stirring at different pH of acidic and neutral medium. At predetermined time intervals of 30mins, 5ml of the samples were withdrawn and immediately replaced with an equal volume of dissolution medium to keep the volume constant. Also, pure antimalarial drug (Artemether) were studied along with silica drug composite to compare the in vitro drug release profile by weighing 2mg of pure antimalarial drugs Artemether and suspended it in 0.5% SLS similar to that of MCM-41-Art. These samples were then properly diluted and analyzed for antimalarial content artemether at 254nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer. The pH effect on the dissolution was studied.

➤ Parasite Inoculation

Blood was taken from a donor mouse, previously infected with *Plasmodium berghei* (NK-65) and diluted with isotonic saline. Percentage parasitemia and red blood cell count of the donor mouse was determined using a haemocytometer. To count the red blood cells, blood was suitably diluted with isotonic diluting fluid to prevent lysis of red blood cells and is counted in a Neubauer counting chamber. The dilution factor that was used is 1:200.

4.0ml of the diluting fluid i.e. 3% formol titrate was dispensed into a test tube. A 20 µl pipette was used to draw up blood. This was then introduced into the diluting fluid. The counting chamber was cleaned to settle and a Pasteur pipette was used to draw some of the diluted blood from the tube to fill the counting chamber. The red cells were allowed to settle in the counting chamber for five minutes. The red cells were counted in five groups of 16 small squares in the central ruled areas of the chamber to make a total of 80 of the small squares. An objective lens will be used to count the cells at x40.

➤ Determination of percentage parasitaemia

To determine the parasitaemia, a drop of blood was collected from the tail of the mice and a glass spreader was used to spread the blood to about 5cm. It was allowed to dry, fixed in methanol and stained with Giemsa stain. The parasitized red blood cells are then counted using the x100 objective (oil immersion).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Drug Carrier Synthesised with Varied ratio of CTAB (MCM-41 and Amino Modified MCM-41)

SN	CARRIER	CTAB (g)	TEOS (ml)	APTES (ml)	ACRONYMS	SURFACTANT REMOVED BY
1	A	1.355	6.7		MCM-41	Calcination
2	B	1.355	6.7	0.54	AMCM-41	Solvent Extraction
3	C	1	6.7		MCM-41	Calcination
4	D	1	6.7	0.54	AMCM-41	Solvent Extraction
5	E	1.642	6.7		MCM-41	Calcination
6	F	1.642	6.7	0.54	AMCM-41	Solvent Extraction

➤ *Loading Of Drugs (Artemether)*

In the course of the loading experiment it was discovered that carrier C and D have the best drug loading capacity, which indicates that the smaller the surfactant template (CTAB) the higher the pore volume. Thus, increase in the drug adsorptive of the carrier. The loading rates of 3hrs have the best drug adsorptive. That is, the carrier (MCM-41 and aMCM-41) was gradually adsorbing the drugs with time until it was fully absorbed/encapsulated in 3hrs. It was discovered that the systems with pH 3.5 (acidic medium) for artemether have the best loading capacity than the systems with pH 7.0 (Neutral Medium).

➤ *Fourier Transform Infrared (Ft-Ir)*

Fig. 2: FT-IR MCM-41

FT-IR characterization of MCM-41 shows the broad band at 3450cm^{-1} may be attributed to surface silanols and the adsorbed water molecule (Si - OH) group. The 1646.40cm^{-1} is attributed to SiO-H bending caused by deformation vibrations of the adsorbed water molecules. The strong 1096.80cm^{-1} band is assigned to internal and external asymmetric Si-O stretching vibrations. The 964cm^{-1} is attributed to Si-O (Silaxone) symmetrical stretching. Also, the 470cm^{-1} is attributed to silaxone (Si-O) bending vibration.

Fig. 3: FT-IR for aMCM-41

Shows the FT-IR characterization of aMCM-41, after amino-functionalization, the band at 3627.20 cm^{-1} for free Silanol (Si-OH) groups was evacuated. The presence of bands at 680.80 , 1468 and 2937 cm^{-1} is assigned to N-H bending vibration, N-H asymmetric bending vibration and C-H link, respectively.

Fig. 4: FT-IR for Artemether (Antimalaria Drug)

The characteristic FT-IR peaks of the pure artemether occurred at C-H stretching at 2957.60 cm^{-1} , C-H bending at 1462.40 cm^{-1} , C-O bending at 1031.20 cm^{-1} , C-O-O-C bending vibration at 1196.80 cm^{-1} , O-O-C stretching at 871.20 cm^{-1} and O-O stretching at 742.40 cm^{-1} respectively.

Fig. 5: FT-IR of Artemether Loaded MCM-41

Shows the FT-IR of arthemeter loaded in MCM-41, it shows the major functional groups of MCM-41 which is an indication that the arthemeter had been well encapsulated by MCM-41.

➤ Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm

Fig. 6: Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of MCM-41

FIG. 7: Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of Artemether

➤ Encapsulated InMCM-41

Fig. 8: Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of aMCM-41

Fig. 9: Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of Artemether Encapsulated In aMCM-41

Figure 6 Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of MCM-41 showing the BET surface areas 131.6077 m²/g and pore volume of 3.1617 nm which is in accordance with a well synthesized MCM-41. Figure 7 shows the graph of the result for Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of arthemeter encapsulated in MCM-41 showing the BET surface areas 201.2754 m²/g and pore volume of 4.3953 nm which shows an increase in the surface area and decrease in pore volume which is an indication that the drug had been encapsulated in MCM-41. Figure 8 show the graph of the result for Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of aMCM-41 showing the BET surface area 159.2630 m²/g and pore volume 2.9778 nm 2.5551 nm which is in accordance with a well synthesized aMCM-41. Figure 9 shows the graph of the result for Nitrogen Physiosorption Isotherm of arthemeter encapsulated in aMCM-41 showing the BET surface areas 184.8063 m²/g and pore volume 2.9778 nm which shows an increase in the surface area and decrease in pore volume which is an indication that the drug had been encapsulated in aMCM-41.

➤ Kinetic Release Of The Encapsulated Drugs And The Free Drugs (In Vitro Study)

Fig. 10: The Kinetic Release of the Encapsulated Drugs and the Free Drugs (In vitro Study)

The in-vitro release studies of the Artemether loaded in MCM-41, aMCM-41, the free drug (Artemether) and Chloroquine as the control from figure 10. It was discovered that Artemether loaded in aMCM-41 have the highest percentage of drug release with time followed by the Artemether loaded in MCM-41 which makes it much better than the parent drugs (Artemether) and the control (Chloroquine).

➤ Invivo Studies

Fig. 11: Chemo suppression analysis using mice

This show the results of chemo suppression analysis whereby Chloroquine was used as positive control which suppresses the antimalarial fully on the third day while water was used as negative control. In the cause of the studies it was discovered that the artemether in MCM-41 and aMCM-41 compared to the parent drugs (artemether) have the best suppression on the malaria parasite.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A well ordered MCM-41 and aMCM-41 were synthesised with three ratio of CTAB (1.355g, 1g, and 1.642g) to 6.7ml of TEOS. It was discovered that MCM-41 and aMCM-41 synthesised with CTAB of 1g to 6.7ml TEOS have the best drug loading capacity and were acronyms as C and D. The antimalaria drugs artemether was loaded in the carriers (MCM-41 and aMCM-41) under the condition of time (1hr, 3hrs and 6hrs), pH (Acidic, Basic and Neutral Medium) and temperature (25 °C and 40 °C). It was observed that the drugs were best loaded in the carrier in 3hrs, Acidic medium and at the temperature of 25 °C.

The synthesised MCM_41 and their nano drugs fit well for their properties as depicted from the FT-IR, N₂ Physiosorption isotherm and invitro kinetic studies. The MCM-41 loaded artemether gives better therapeutic performance over other nano drugs and their parent drugs (artemether). These lend credence to the use of nano carrier for high potency effectiveness of antimalarial drugs delivery.

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